

TRANSFORMATIONAL AND INNOVATIVE PRINCIPLES OF MANAGING YOUTH ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15192981>

Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan, the deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition, and the prospects for the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition. The deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition are also analyzed.

Key words: youth economic activity, social laws, tradition and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic and functional, deterministic basis, culture of healthy competition.

INTRODUCTION

Radical qualitative changes in society, sociocreative innovations, and the demands of civil society are emerging in the context of a market economy. The traditional economy is being improved under the influence of new societal demands and the innovative environment, and it is institutionalizing due to transformational processes. These institutional and functional changes are having a significant qualitative impact on the economic activity of young people. Social progress introduces a new quality into the architecture of values, creating a new general axiological layer in society. The transition from the old, traditional way of thinking to a new, innovative one naturally begins with the youth sector of society. "In order to achieve prosperity in life, a person must live understanding the changes, because development is driven not by stagnant thoughts but by innovations." Understanding the dialectical connection between innovative thinking and transformational processes is essential for activating youth in social, economic, and political spheres.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

The economic activity of young people has been reflected in the scientific observations of F. Primov, Y. Ernazarova, Sh. Quvondiqov, J. Mavlyanov, and Sh. Azamatov. In the CIS countries, scholars such as G.P. Voshanova, G.S. Godzina, L.G. Golovach, V.Y. Savchenko, D. Saxal, D.I. Kokurin, O.A. Latuxa, A.D. Sheremet,

Y.V. Sherbinina have conducted research. These researchers have focused on the changes in socio-economic life after the post-totalitarian system, systematic transformation processes, the realization of economic rights and freedoms in national contexts, the development of business and entrepreneurship, and the issues related to innovation in scientific, technical, and societal development. The scientific theoretical and socio-philosophical conclusions, analysis methods, and sociometric observations from their works are significant for our own research. Among foreign scholars, E. Porter, E. Maykl, K.Y. Totyev, A.Y. Yudanov, G.L. Azoyev, A.P. Gradov, M.V. Konotopov, R.A. Fatkhutdinov, A.Y. Kibanov have studied various issues of improving competition processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Uzbekistan, a necessary legal framework and conditions have been created to diversify property relations and develop free economic activity. The State Property Management and Privatization Committee and its regional structures have been established and are operating successfully. Furthermore, commodity, raw material, and securities exchanges, commercial banking systems, chambers of commerce, business funds, and various consulting, leasing, and other market infrastructures have emerged. As a result of privatization, non-state properties joint-stock companies, corporations, transnational associations, firms, companies, joint ventures, and individual entrepreneurs have been formed. The new economic value system that has emerged is shaping terms such as "new owner," "investor," and "competition" in the economic consciousness of young people. The formation of the middle class, which will make up the majority of society in the near future, depends entirely on the economic consciousness, culture, and education of young people, which will unite their economic activity. The economic activity of youth is not a sudden historical process; rather, it is a dynamic process emerging due to the intensification of societal transformation and innovation. According to researcher N. Jo'rayev, the market economy, which opened the way for socio-economic transformations, has had a permanent impact on the formation of economic activity in Uzbekistan: "Firstly, the freedom of all forms of property, the opening of personal initiative and entrepreneurship, and the support of business; secondly, the acceleration of privatization processes for economic revitalization, the expansion of property and ownership rights; thirdly, the introduction of a national currency, the ensuring of the value and stability of our currency, which has just entered the global financial markets; fourthly, the recognition of agriculture and rural life as a traditional and important sector in economic

policy; fifthly, the restoration of past cultures and values, the development of a concept and theory of economic reforms and consistent measures in this regard" have all influenced the motivational and culminative aspects of youth economic activity.

In society, various evolutionary, revolutionary (social, political, economic, and spiritual-cultural) changes are explained by the concept of "transformation." What does this concept mean? The term "transformation" emerged in the last century, yet these events—particularly those related to social existence and processes resulting from human activities—have always been associated with transformation, as they have been inherent features and characteristics of such processes.

Although transformational changes are an inherent feature of social development, there is no single model suitable for all nations, ethnic groups, and states. Each people, nation, and state develops and implements it in accordance with its strategic goals.

The word "transformation" comes from Latin, meaning "change," "reorganization," or "to alter into another form." With the emergence of national republics, the category of "transformation" began to be used to refer to processes aimed at changing and renewing society.

The existing changes naturally reflect on people's moral-aesthetic values. In the transition of social needs to a new environment, the renewal of system components can be explained by the concept of "innovation," while the selection and categorization of value systems falls within the scope of "transformation."

According to researcher R. Roziyeva, "there are two layers in moral values—the core (unchangeable) and the upper layer (adaptation to social relations). Adaptation to the demands of social development mainly occurs in the upper layer. The transformation of moral values in accordance with social development demands also occurs through the upper layer. The first, the core part, cannot even be changed by social revolutions, while the second part can be altered by daily needs, external influences, integration relations, and informational flows in accordance with daily needs, leading to transformation."

Transformational changes that emerge under the influence of social development gradually introduce qualitative changes into all forms of social consciousness, including moral, legal, political, and so on. These complex changes can have either a positive or negative impact on the activity of youth. Legal and regulatory documents, as well as presidential decrees and decisions, regulate and control the creation of a dynamic business environment among

youth and the formation of entrepreneurial personalities. Transformational and innovative processes encourage individuals to choose their life positions and be more active for the new era. In this regard, the improvement of values in society, the management of consciousness flows, and the control of the education and enlightenment sector require an institutional approach. Today, the primary goal of the state's innovation policy is shaped and implemented based on the recognition of priorities for increasing the competitiveness of local products, ensuring stable economic growth, improving the quality of life, fostering innovation activity, and ensuring technological and ecological security.

In managing the economic activity of youth, existing transformational and innovative changes interact and require the development of the following network of principles. We outline them as follows:

1. The principle of complexity, meaning taking into account extraverted and introverted factors influencing youth economic activity;
2. The principle of networking, meaning the construction of a generalized model for managing youth economic activity, the creation of a theoretical model of activation, and reflecting the interaction between the general goal and actual state;
3. The principle of ensuring youth participation in the development of innovative business and the practical application of youth policy;
4. The principle of fostering a fair attitude towards labor, i.e., the main motivation for shaping professional skills should be the purpose of labor activity, ensuring a high status for youth in society;
5. The principle of improving the state's continuous management network to maintain the dynamic power of youth economic activity, that is, the creation of a mechanism for working with the "Youth Union";
6. The principle of fostering youth in an active environment, adding them to the reserve for management, developing leadership, shaping leadership ethics, and continuing network work on the education of active youth.

CONCLUSION

These principles provide the opportunity to manage and control youth economic activity during periods of innovative and transformational changes, while also improving, directing, and providing motivational impulses to them. The renewal of consciousness is not a self-occurring process. It lies in the synthesis of deep transformational processes. The goal of youth's innovative economic activity is to create economic, legal, and organizational conditions to increase the competitiveness of local products, make effective use of scientific

and technological achievements, solve socio-economic development problems, and strengthen the country's defense capabilities, as well as ensuring the security of individuals, society, and the state. An increase in youth's economic activity may manifest in two ways: first, economic concepts emerging from transformational changes in society may undermine moral values; second, a growing conservative attitude towards innovation within the existing value system could emerge. Therefore, it is essential to develop a network of principles and action plans to protect youth's economic activity from various influences and to develop it purposefully.

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